

INTEGRATED EDUCATION OPPORTUNITIES IN MODERN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Аннотация. В статье анализируется потенциал и возможности метода смешанного обучения как дидактического средства реализации перехода с традиционной модели обучения на интегрированную с привлечением электронных сред и ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: смешанное обучение, информационные технологии, электронное обучение, информатизация образования.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Abstract. The article analyzes the potential and possibilities of the mixed learning method as a didactic means of implementing the transition from the traditional learning model to an integrated one with the involvement of electronic media and resources.

Keywords: blended learning, information technologies, e-learning, informatization of education.

The Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 serves as a road map for new reforms in the field of education. The content of the concept reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. In it, the improvement of the quality of education, the introduction of digital technologies and educational platforms, the involvement of young people in scientific activities, the formation of innovative structures, the commercialization of the results of scientific research, the achievement of international recognition, and many other specific directions are defined in the cross-section of years, periods and sectors. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality [1].

Article 16 of the Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Distance education is aimed at obtaining the necessary knowledge, skills and skills by students using information and communication technologies and the Internet global information network, in accordance with curricula and educational programs. ... In the implementation of educational programs, e-learning and distance learning technologies can be used in various forms of education" [2].

Electronic education - organization of educational activities by using the content of the database, information used in the implementation of educational programs, information technologies used in processing this information, technical tools, as well as information and telecommunication networks that ensure the transmission of information through communication channels, interaction between students and pedagogical staff. are communications, and distance learning technologies are indirect (distance) educational technologies that implement the interaction of teachers and students with the help of information and telecommunication networks [3].

One of the modern educational technologies is blended learning, based on the concept of combining "auditory education system", electronic education and distance learning technologies.

The main advantages of this education are:

- planning and understanding that the educational need will satisfy the learner and lead to the expected results;
- provision of effective educational management tools;
- traditional education reduces the time and financial expenses allocated to education without losing its advantage;
- education and technology enrich and complement each other;
- students have active social interaction with each other and with the teacher;
- not choosing the time and place of training;
- variety of didactic approaches in the educational process;
- to improve the quality of education by using effective educational and methodological tools;
- adaptability of the educational trajectory, etc.

As we can see, the implementation of mixed education fully meets the requirements of the state educational standard, that is, it can be used and must be used.

Basic definitions of blended learning:

1. Blended learning is a formal curriculum in which learners study at least partially in an electronic-online format and at the same time have elements of control over time, course and pace of learning; classes are partly held outside the auditoriums. This education uses a variety of methods to provide an integrated learning experience.

2. Blended learning is a planned and pedagogical integration of electronic and traditional learning.

3. Blended education is an educational method that combines various resources, in particular, elements of traditional training and electronic education [4, 5, 6, 7].

The use of traditional and electronic educational methods and technologies allows to use the advantages of these forms of education at the same time. Elements of traditional education are based on direct personal interactions between learners and teachers, serving to motivate learners.

E-Learning technologies provide multimedia content across time and space for learners with different capabilities and requests. The combination of online and offline learning elements makes learning efficient, cost-effective, and makes the learning process interactive, person-centered, and flexible for stakeholders.

Of course, there are several reasons for ineffective use of distance and e-learning technologies:

- lack of effective educational management tools;
- lack of funds for the development of educational content;
- lack of teachers in the field of distance learning technologies;
- specific characteristics of education;
- lack of modern teaching tools;
- delay of educational programs from real life, etc.

It should also be noted that education based on Internet technologies is "a form of modern education". It is natural that there are some disadvantages of using new technologies in education today.

In the blended learning model, it is possible to design courses step by step, this model does not need fully interactive and multimedia courses. The use of the mixed education method in the educational process allows solving a number of tasks:

1. For learners:

- to expand the educational opportunities of learners by increasing the availability and flexibility of education, taking into account the individual educational needs of learners and the pace of mastering educational materials;

- implementation of individual educational plans with a large selection of subjects, their level of development and methods of organizing educational activities;

- personalization of the educational process: independently determines the educational goal of the learner, the ways to achieve it, taking into account educational needs, interests and abilities;

- assessment procedure and maximum objectivity of results;

- to encourage the formation of the subjective position of learners: independence, social activity, cognitive activity;

- to get personal advice from the teacher to overcome difficulties in mastering educational materials and gaps in knowledge.

2. For teachers:

- improving the qualification of pedagogic personnel;

- acquisition of professional competences aimed at introducing new generation state education standards;

- to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity in order to achieve new educational results;

- use of new types of control and communication in the pedagogical process;

- organization of quality work with highly motivated learners;

- changing the teacher's style: engaging in interactive communication with the learner in the transfer of knowledge.

3. When organizing the educational process:

- the possibility of saving money by increasing the level of efficiency of pedagogical activity;

- attracting an additional contingent of learners by organizing multidisciplinary training;

- solving the problem of lack of pedagogical personnel;

- strengthening educational activities in order to save time for the realization of other educational and cultural needs.

Examples of the organization of blended learning: e-courses, working on specific projects, e-books, mobile learning, podcasts, day courses, learning games and simulations, etc.

There are typical models of blended learning that can be chosen as a basis:

1. "Face-to-Face Driver" model: most of the curriculum is taught in the educational institution with direct contact with teachers, and e-learning is used in addition to the main program.

2. Rotation Model (Rotation Model) is a model in which there is a transition from one direction to another (student exchange) within the study of a course or educational topic.

3. Flex model (flexible model): effective use of e-learning; providing support to teachers in online, offline and full-time learning formats; availability of an individual schedule; work in small groups; organization of group projects and individual education;

4. Self-blend model (learning menu model): study one or more e-learning courses completely online; organizing training in different institutions at the same time.

5. Enriched virtual educational model (virtual enriched model): working model of an educational institution; voluntary attendance at an educational institution; a combination of daytime and remote training.

Each model is distinguished by the dominance of one of the three components of blended learning technology:

1. Direct personal interaction of the participants of the educational process.

2. Interactive cooperation through computer-telecommunication technologies and electronic information-educational resources.

3. Self-management and training.

In this type of education, students are listeners, teachers are tutors, and dean's staff are organizers of the educational process.

The activity of the teacher is to coordinate daytime and distance learning activities of learners in a high-tech information-educational environment, to build individual educational trajectories, to organize various types of activities using information-educational resources, to select the content of electronic education.

In mixed educational conditions, the teacher provides feedback on the development of the learner and the rate of mastering of educational materials through videoconference, forum, chat and other information-educational conditions. In addition, the teacher constantly monitors the educational process and comprehensively analyzes the results of the learner's activities, by checking the network activity data, the quality of test control work, the number of attempts to complete one or another task, and references to additional educational resources. performs the analysis [8].

The traditional approach to study abroad is called teacher-centered. In this approach, the teacher becomes the manager of the learning process. In the blended learning model, the approach changes to student-centered. In traditional education, the learner is taught, while in blended education, he is supported. Participant of the educational process - Active Student (active student) can adapt the educational process and plan the study time independently. The learner's independent work consists of learning educational materials online, working in chats and forums, communicating via e-mail, passing online tests.

E-mail, chat, forum are the main elements that enable students to work with the help of information and communication tools and their interactions. The main difference of these elements from personal communication is asynchronous, anonymous effect, lack of "live" communication, presence of a large audience.

The main elements of the blended learning model:

1. Lecture sessions: lecture materials are prepared in the form of a presentation and/or an online course.

2. Seminar training (face-to-face sessions): training in this form can be combined with lectures. It involves discussion of important features and topics of science, as well as practical application of skills.

3. Teaching materials of the subjects (textbooks and study guides): materials are presented in printed and electronic form, and various multimedia applications can be used.

4. Online communication between the teacher and students.

5. Individual and group online projects (collaboration): developing skills for working on the Internet, analyzing information from various sources, working with a group, distributing tasks, and feeling responsible for doing work.

6. Virtual audience: communication of students with the teacher using various Internet communication tools.

7. Audio-video lectures, presentations and simulations.

For online classes, it is necessary to independently master certain materials or perform tasks independently. It can be conducted according to the "question-answer" scheme or by discussing a certain topic. In mixed education, the duration of tasks is determined: "before" work, "during" work, "after" work.

Web 2.0 collaboration tools such as social networks, content, wikis, and blogs are used to facilitate student-teacher collaboration. Assessment of academic performance of learners can be done online as well as in the classroom [8].

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